

STRATEGIES FOR ENHANCING COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE IN THE EFL CLASSROOM

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13935035>

ANNOTATION

This research aims to explore the strategies used in EFL (English as a Foreign Language) learners is to encourage students to engage in classroom interaction, even if they have low English proficiency. To foster communication in an EFL classroom, teachers need to apply various strategies throughout the teaching and learning process. These strategies serve as a bridge to facilitate interaction among learners. Given that some EFL learners find it challenging to communicate in a foreign language, they must be motivated, supported, and encouraged to interact with others.

Key words: teaching strategies, EFL learner, communicative language teaching (CLT), limited English.

СТРАТЕГИИ ПОВЫШЕНИЯ КОММУНИКАТИВНОЙ КОМПЕТЕНТНОСТИ НА КЛАССАХ EFL

АННОТАЦИЯ

Целью данного исследования является изучение стратегий, используемых в изучающих английский как иностранный (EFL), чтобы побудить учащихся к взаимодействию в классе, даже если у них низкий уровень владения английским языком. Чтобы способствовать общению в классе EFL, учителям необходимо применять различные стратегии на протяжении всего процесса преподавания и обучения. Эти стратегии служат мостом для облегчения взаимодействия между учащимися. Учитывая, что некоторым изучающим EFL сложно общаться на иностранном языке, их необходимо мотивировать, поддерживать и поощрять к взаимодействию с другими.

Ключевые слова: стратегии обучения, изучающий EFL, коммуникативное обучение языку (CLT), ограниченный английский.

INTRODUCTION

Despite extensive research on Communicative Language Teaching (CLT), few studies have specifically examined teachers' strategies for fostering student engagement in EFL settings. This research addresses that gap by investigating the teaching strategies that support classroom communication within the CLT framework. The research aims to shed light on how teachers identify and implement these strategies to enhance communication with students.

The study's findings aim to detail the teacher's role in applying CLT principles in an EFL classroom, focusing on how communication is fostered beyond grammatical accuracy to encompass holistic elements, as suggested by Richards (2006). Effective communication is understood here to include not only grammar but also linguistic, discourse, and strategic aspects, which contribute to a well-rounded communicative competence.

LITERATURE REVIEW AND METHODOLOGY

According to Hymes [1], communicative competence refers to the mastery and ability to use grammatical knowledge effectively across various communicative situations. He

differentiates competence from capacity: while communicative competence involves understanding linguistic and sociolinguistic norms, capacity is the ability to apply this understanding to create meaning in language use. Hymes further distinguishes that ability is not considered a part of competence. Widdowson, on the other hand, was one of the first to emphasize the importance of performance, or real language use, in the relationship between competence and performance. [2]

Communicative competence is seen as a combination of both knowledge and skills necessary for effective communication. In this framework, knowledge includes an individual's awareness (either conscious or unconscious) of language and how it is used. [3] This knowledge is categorized into three areas: understanding grammatical rules, knowing how to use language in social contexts to achieve communicative functions, and understanding how to combine sentences and communicative functions according to discourse principles. Additionally, the concept of skill pertains to an individual's ability to apply this knowledge in real-life communication. [4]

Data were gathered through three methods: observation, interview, and questionnaire. Classroom observations were conducted to examine the teaching and learning processes, while interviews were held with the teacher to collect relevant data. The students' input was obtained through a questionnaire, ensuring a comprehensive understanding of the classroom dynamics.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Here are some strategies for enhancing communicative competence in the EFL classroom: [5, 1-19]

1. **Task-Based Learning:** Use real-life tasks (such as ordering food, asking for directions, or discussing daily routines) to provide learners with authentic contexts for communication.
2. **Role-Playing and Simulations:** Engage students in role-playing exercises, which simulate real-world scenarios, helping them practice conversational skills in a safe environment.
3. **Group Work and Pair Activities:** Encourage interaction by using pair or group work, promoting cooperation, active listening, and communication skills among peers.
4. **Information Gap Activities:** Design activities where students must share information with each other to complete a task. This encourages meaningful exchanges and requires learners to use language to bridge knowledge gaps.
5. **Storytelling and Narration:** Have students share personal stories or create narratives based on prompts. This builds confidence in speaking and fluency, fostering greater ease in verbal expression.
6. **Using Visual and Multimedia Aids:** Integrate videos, images, or audio clips related to cultural or conversational themes to spark discussion and enhance listening comprehension.
7. **Question-Answer Drills:** Use targeted question-answer activities to help students formulate responses quickly and naturally, building reflexive conversational skills.
8. **Feedback and Error Correction:** Offer constructive feedback on language use during activities, focusing on encouraging natural fluency over perfection, and gently correcting recurring mistakes.
9. **Classroom Language Practice:** Create opportunities for students to use English consistently in the classroom through everyday tasks, such as asking for materials, explaining homework, or managing group activities in English.

10. **Encouraging Self-Expression:** Allow students to discuss personal opinions or present topics they are passionate about. This increases motivation and personal investment in language learning.

Each of these strategies aims to create a supportive and engaging environment that fosters students' confidence, fluency, and overall communicative competence.

Teaching and learning English in the classroom often present challenges, particularly in the context of EFL instruction. The limited opportunities for students to use English in their daily lives contribute to their lack of familiarity with the language in real-world interactions. Additionally, cultural norms, classroom traditions, and established teaching paradigms can also influence the practical use of English beyond the classroom. Common challenges encountered during classroom interaction include difficulties with grammar, vocabulary, and maintaining student motivation. [6, 28-35]

CONCLUSION

Students who grow up with limited exposure to English face several issues in the learning process, including a lack of habit in using the language, which impacts the way they engage with lessons. As a result, teachers need to apply a variety of strategies to address these challenges and encourage students to participate in meaningful communication activities. The teacher's readiness and creativity in managing the classroom environment are key to finding engaging and enjoyable teaching methods that help students overcome these obstacles and improve their communicative competence.

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